

Revamping Teacher Education from the Lens of NEP 2020

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Abstract

Increasing concerns in the area of teacher education are gaining attention, bringing the analysis of policies and decision-making related to teacher education into the spotlight. Improving the quality of teaching-learning has always remained the central focus of all policy pronouncements and programmes. The present paper highlights the imperative need to restructure the existing curriculum of teacher preparation and continuous development of teachers to align with contemporary educational paradigms that emphasise dynamism. The paper gives a brief overview of the developments that guided the growth of the discipline of teacher education over the years. Traditional approaches to teacher preparation often fall short in equipping educators with the requisite skills and perspectives to navigate the complexities of modern classrooms. By revamping the existing programme through a progressive and responsive approach under the proposed Integrated Teacher Education Programme (ITEP), institutions can better prepare educators to address the different kinds of needs of students and effectively navigate the evolving landscape of education. It concludes that academic improvement requires the continuous involvement of different stakeholders.

Keywords: Educational Paradigm, Integrated Teacher Education Programme, Revamping, Stakeholders

Introduction

The famous statement from the statesperson Dr. S. Radhakrishnan, first Vice-President and second President of Independent India and an ardent believer of the transformative power of education, that 'Teacher is the Nation Builder' speaks loudly about the character of teacher and the necessity to establish good teachers. Teacher education programmes focus on building teacher proficiency and competence. The development process should equip them to face new challenges emerging due to advancements in technology and different areas. There is a need to design innovative teacher education programmes that encompass various approaches. This would help student teachers learn to respond dynamically. Conventional knowledge and skills alone cannot produce intelligent and progressive teachers. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 has clearly stated, "The quality of teacher education, recruitment, deployment, service conditions and empowerment of teachers is not where it should be, and consequently the quality and motivation of teachers does not reach the desired standards. The high respect for teachers and high status of the teaching profession must be restored to inspire the best to enter the teaching profession" (NEP para 5.1). The bright future of children and progress of the country can

be accelerated by having sufficient resources of aroused and invested teachers.

Several policy documents advocate for strong interconnections between higher education and teacher education (The Kothari Commission Report, 1964-66; Report of The Committee to Advise on Renovation and Rejuvenation of Higher Education, 2009; National Education Policy, 2020). The challenges in improving teacher education programs and practices are enormous, and a qualified teaching force is an unquestionable necessity. Recognizing the urgent need to reform teacher education, NEP 2020 made comprehensive recommendations endorsing a complete overhaul of the existing policies and plans pertaining to higher education (NEP para 9.3). This is going to have implications for the preparation and development of teachers and educators. The policy seeks to inculcate 21st-century skills in children (para 21.6) and make the country's education more inclusive and flexible. It recognizes that teachers play a crucial role in achieving these goals and transforming the content and delivery of education in India.

Therefore, the policy has impressed upon a paradigm change in the visualization and operationalisation of the teacher education system in the country. NEP 2020 seeks to kick-start various systemic changes to encourage bright

and talented young minds to pursue the teaching profession.

Teacher education is vital in creating a pool of school teachers that will shape the next generation. Teacher preparation is an activity that requires multidisciplinary perspectives and knowledge, formation of dispositions and values, and development of practice under the best mentors. Teachers must be grounded in Indian values, languages, knowledge, ethos, and traditions including tribal traditions, while also being well-versed in the latest advances in education and pedagogy (NEP para 15.1). According to the National Education Policy (NEP para 15.6), HEIs offering teacher education programmes will ensure the availability of experts in education and related disciplines as well as specialized subjects. Each higher education institution will have a network of government and private schools to work closely with, where potential teachers will student-teach and participate in other activities such as community service, adult and vocational education, etc. This will help in fostering a holistic and practical approach to teacher preparation.

Criticality of the Position of 'Teacher' and Teacher Development

The 'Teacher' is a vital agent determining the extent of success of the educational system in a country. There is a close link between the three components of teaching-learning: the Teacher, the process, and the techniques of teaching, and the preparation of teachers. Their interrelation and interconnectedness are almost axiomatic (Mehrotra, 2006). The value and worth of serving teachers are guided by the quality of entrants to the pre-service teacher preparation programmes. Secondly, the level and education of teacher educators are the strategic factors that affect the performance and skills of teachers undergoing training, whether pre-service or in-service. Here, the position of a teacher educator, her/his competence, capability, and scholarship become very significant (Verma Commission, 2012). The educational discourse during the past few decades, especially post-NCF 2005, has brought a change in the conduct of teaching, teachers' engagement with learners, and learners' engagement with knowledge gaining. Teaching is no longer considered synonymous with the transfer of facts and knowledge. Instead, a teacher's task is to facilitate learning by enabling the child to construct or generate knowledge based on his/her own reflections, encounters, experimentation, analysis, and reflection. This shift in thinking about a teacher's task is built on the premise that children have the potential to construct knowledge, make meaning, and think independently, given a conducive and challenging pedagogic environment. The National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education, 2009 converges with these ideas and describes the dream teacher envisioned for an education that addresses issues of quality and equity. It states that teachers should be willing to care for children and enjoy their company. They should be keen to spread the knowledge and skill base of their students. They should not be shy to take

responsibility towards the community and larger society, understand the untold problems of their students, and display a strong commitment to justice with a progressive mindset toward the renewal process of social thought. Teachers need to have confidence in the abilities and creativity of their students, and they should be enabled to become active participants in their own learning and not mere recipients of knowledge. They need to move towards competency-based learning, shifting away from rote learning or exam-oriented learning. Teachers should be mentored in organizing learner-centered, activity-based, and experiential learning activities.

Evolution of Teacher Education as a Discipline

Teacher education programmes have been in existence for a very long time. In the 1850s, teacher training was a common course intended to prepare good educators for schools. Subsequently, teacher preparation courses became more specialized following the suggestions of the Indian Education Commission in 1882; the added component was shorter duration programmes for graduates. The twentieth century witnessed greater variations in courses with respect to the stages of school education -primary, elementary, secondary, and so on. Alongside, training modes were diversified. Regular campus-cum-practicing school experience, correspondence-cum-contact programmes, and later distance education mode came into being. (National Focus Group on Teacher Education for Curriculum Renewal, 2006). With the passage of time, teacher preparation was acknowledged as an integral factor of the educational system, deemed essential for both elementary and secondary school teachers. The traditional practice, where teachers received training while working, underwent a significant transformation, and full-time, pre-service teacher education training programmes were conceptualized and initiated (NCTE, 1998). Training programmes were designed to respond to the specific requirements of elementary and secondary school teachers.

Pre-service teacher education programmes represent the first form of professional training individuals undergo to embark on a teaching career. These programmes integrate theoretical knowledge about teaching with practical field experiences. It equips teachers with the foundational competence necessary for proficiently delivering the curriculum. India has one of the world's largest teacher education systems. Teacher education is provided by university departments of education and affiliated colleges, government and government-aided institutions, private and self-financing colleges, and open universities. Despite the fact that most teacher education programmes are practically identical, the quality varies amongst institutions and universities.

As there was a steep rise in the number of teacher education institutions and the involvement of the private sector, upholding quality standards has become progressively challenging. Various programmes and policy actions have repeatedly acknowledged the urgent need for

a comprehensive restructuring of teacher education programmes to ensure quality maintenance. There are many studies and research findings which support this fact.

Dutta, 2022 points out that the delivery of the teacher education program has not changed much even after revamping the curriculum, as Teacher Education Institutes (TEIs) are generally suffering from various unhealthy practices that are damaging to the profession. A long internship is suggested as a practical way to develop appropriate attitudes and dispositions along with the necessary skills to become a good teacher.

However, it is not an exception that student teachers deliver isolated lesson plans in classrooms in a mechanical way. They are not faced with situations that could prepare them for the roles of facilitators or counselors. Reflective teaching is also discussed as an important component for both pre-service and in-service teacher training, but again, this is hardly seen in practice.

Sharma (2022) explains the major challenges to creating a more dynamic and rigorous teacher education program, including the lack of good reading material, teacher trainees' lack of content knowledge, and the struggle to balance between exposing students to theoretical ideas and practical experiences simultaneously. One of the major challenges is to find relevant, content-specific, and easy-to-consume reading material. The available materials are highly theoretical and academic, and on the other side, the material is an overly simplistic version of popular theories. There is a need to have good reading material that allows for deep engagement and critical reflection. Also, there is a need for literature based on teachers' experiences and observations that can be useful for the student teachers while they are pursuing the course. Implementation of the Integrated Teacher Education Programme (ITEP), as suggested by NEP 2020, to bring transformation in the area of teacher preparation is due to take place. Some publications have given a reflective view on the structure and components of ITEP along with its implementation challenges.

Sreekanth (2024) published one research article based on the research conducted to review the entry-level and exit-level (at the end of the programme), students' opinions about the programme and the opportunities available to them after the conclusion of the programme. It is worth mentioning that the Regional Institutes of Education of the NCERT are already running 4-year B.Ed. Integrated course and this research is connected to that.

The findings reveal that students generally feel contented with the programme, with some hiccups like traditional teaching methods, the curriculum is content-loaded, etc. However, they receive ample job opportunities, which is indicative of the acceptance in the field regarding the worth of the programme. The suggestions of the respondents are that instead of three majors in the undergraduate programme, it could be a single major (one subject only), along with pedagogy as a second major. This

suggestion is in alignment with recommendations of the National Education Policy – 2020 and ITEP.

Mohanty (2022) does not appreciate the idea of having an experiment on ITEP in 50 multidisciplinary institutions. The central government may decide to establish (a) its own autonomous teacher training institution in every state and union territory and have infrastructure similar to the existing regional institutes and consider these as autonomous teacher degrees awarding teacher training institutions (b) establish a Central University for Teacher Education, (c) establish a National Mission on Teachers and Teaching as suggested in the Twelfth Five Year Plan document. Of course, it would be subject to availability of funds and approvals by the policy planners and implementers.

Chitra (2019) expresses hope in ITEP, saying that how current policy focus on pre-service teacher education presents a major opportunity to significantly improve this critical component for making a high-quality education system. An examination of the existing effective practices can provide a strong foundation for further reform. It is an undisputed argument that the teacher is at the centre of the thinking while conceptualising small or big changes in the teaching-learning process.

All endeavors need to be directed to motivate teachers to become groundbreaking and creative. It goes without saying that a self-motivated and industrious teacher can utilize his or her own resources to keep him or herself abreast of new developments in the field. It has been conceded that at least pre-service teacher education programmes should enable their teacher graduates to respond enthusiastically to the challenges in the area of teaching and teacher education. Only then teachers can be real contributors toward the national development.

Vision of NEP 2020 and National Curriculum Framework for School Education (NCFSE) 2023 on Developing Teachers

NEP 2020 places 'Teacher' as the key factor for bringing paradigm changes in the entire education system. It states that, "Education Policy must help re-establish teachers, at all levels, as the most respected and essential members of our society, because they truly shape our next generation of citizens. It must do everything to empower teachers and help them to do their job as effectively as possible" (NEP pg. 4).

The NEP 2020 aims to bring such changes in the teacher education system that are likely to have far-reaching implications for the planning and administration of these programmes.

The dream of the policymakers is that "By 2030, the minimum degree qualifications for teaching will be a four-year integrated B.Ed. degree that teaches a range of knowledge content and pedagogy and includes strong practicum training in the form of student-teaching at local schools" (Para 5.23 of NEP).

“The two-year B.Ed. will be offered by the same institution offering four-year integrated B.Ed. and will be intended for those who have already obtained bachelor’s degree in specialised subjects.” Further, “These B.Ed. programmes will be suitably adopted as one-year B.Ed. programme and will be offered to those who have completed the equivalent of 4-year multi-disciplinary bachelor’s degree or who have obtained a Master’s degree in a specialty and wish to become a subject teacher in that specialty” (Para 5.23).

Besides modifications in the Pre-service teacher education programmes, the policymakers have recognised the need for continuous professional development of teachers while they are in service. In this regard the policy mentions that *“Each teacher will be expected to participate in at least 50 hours of CPD opportunities every year for their own professional development. During the CPD, particular opportunities will be offered to cover the latest pedagogies and formative and adaptive assessments” (Para 5.15).* Also, *“School principals and school complex leaders will also undergo 50 hours or more of CPD per year covering leadership and management as well as content and pedagogy and competency-based education” (Para 5.16).* The four-year pre-service teacher education programme has been called the ‘Integrated Teacher Education Programme (ITEP),’ which is discussed in the following sections.

The National Curriculum Framework for School Education, 2023 acknowledges that having adept and committed teachers is a dire need to make learning meaningful and real. *“Supportive environments within schools and the ecosystem improve Teacher effectiveness”.* They must feel happy to join a well-qualified, supportive, and energetic group of professionals. There should be a conducive infrastructure and environment with essential facilities and adequate learning resources, including teaching-learning supplies to engage students in a joyful way. While these enablers are critical, they are not sufficient in themselves. Teachers know about the needs of their students, and they are the best at finding solutions to meet their needs. This calls for autonomy for teachers to bring desirable shifts in our schools and classrooms.

The NCFSE, 2023 also takes a view of the existing pre-service and in-service teacher education programmes. The framework suggests that the pre-service programs must equip teachers with a strong foundation, having a fine blend of knowledge, skills, and attitude. This can be best achieved through an interdisciplinary curriculum and good experience of practical situations in the school. The vision expressed in the framework is that the four-year programme, ITEP, outlined in NEP 2020, will provide good practical exposure to Student Teachers. There would be opportunities for interactions and discussions with peers, teacher educators, and teachers of the schools, which will help them in linking their academic knowledge with practice, thus bridging the gap between theory and practice. The four-year Integrated Teacher Education Programme (ITEP) curriculum must take into account the guiding principles related to the curriculum and pedagogy, as suggested under NCFSE.

ITEP- Outcome-based Approach for Teacher Preparation

The Integrated Teacher Education Programme (ITEP), developed as a follow-up of the recommendations of the NEP 2020, envisages an outcome-based approach to teacher preparation. This entails a specific emphasis on the Graduate attributes to be demonstrated by the student teachers. Graduate attributes express the expected characteristics of a graduate student-teacher, including her knowledge, abilities, skills, values, and dispositions.

Curricular Structure of ITEP

The curricular structure of the ITEP comprises three elements- Curricular Components, Approach to Curriculum Transaction, and Approach to Assessment and Evaluation. The Curricular and Pedagogical Principles guiding ITEP suggest a curriculum that combines a strong theoretical understanding of the foundations of education, educational perspectives, subjects of study, and pedagogy with wide practice and experience. Sufficient opportunities should be provided to the student teachers to think and reflect intensely on educational ideas and connect with regional and local contexts. They should be able to see connections within and across the courses and between theory and practice.

Fig. Curricular Structure of ITEP

Curricular Components of ITEP

There are seven curricular components of ITEP. Each component with credits assigned is as follows.

- Student Induction Programme*
- Foundations of Education (30 credits)
- Disciplinary/interdisciplinary Courses (64 credits)
- Stage-specific Content-cum-Pedagogy Courses (16 credits)
- Ability Enhancement and Value-Added Courses (28 credits)
- School experience, including Internship in Teaching (20 credits)
- Community Engagement and Service (2 credits)

**The induction programme will be organised during the first two weeks of the first semester*

Approach to Curriculum Transaction

The approach will focus on achieving competencies and learning outcomes by trainee teachers. Practicum would link theory with practice, and the classroom processes will include lectures supported by tutorials, practicum and field-based learning, and exposure to different types of schools and teacher education institutions.

Approach to Assessment and Evaluation

The ITEP suggests that priority will be given to formative assessment. The methods and techniques of assessment should encourage better student engagement and thorough study. The assessment weightage to different elements will be placed into two categories: learning in actual practice and student learning in reflective and consolidating work.

Role of NCERT in Shaping Teacher Education

The National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) has performed a significant role in giving direction to teacher education. Before the establishment of NCTE, the NCERT was the national body to provide guidance both for school education and teacher education at the national level. Development of curriculum frameworks, publishing resource material, conducting research studies on existing practices, providing pre-service and in-service teacher training and providing guidelines and setting standards for teachers and other institutions working for teachers and teacher educators are some of the major activities undertaken at the NCERT for improving the quality of teacher education. The Council has five Regional Institutes of Education (RIEs) in respective zones of the country. NCERT has pioneered the four-year integrated programme for pre-service teacher education through its RIEs. Adaptive pedagogy and long internships are some of the ways in which the gap between theory and practice can be bridged. The series of NISHTHA (National Initiative for School Heads' and Teachers' Holistic Advancement) programmes for in-service teacher training on various themes is a major step of the NCERT to

update the teachers at all levels and make them proficient in pedagogy, assessment and content creation.

Conclusion

Teacher preparation plays a paramount role in improving the quality of education in India. The sharp rise of privatization of teacher education and the withdrawal of state agencies in establishing public-funded teacher education have created a complexity for transforming teacher education during the past few years. Private institutions in urban areas have contributed to regional inequalities in accessing teacher education programmes. Teacher education establishments and programmes are witnessing variations regarding their location, context, funding, and management. The extended and longer duration of pre-service teacher preparation, i.e., 2-year, 3-year, and 4-year, as suggested by the latest education policy, have already been implemented in selected institutions. The recommendations for the changing structure of teacher education courses assume that longer duration will succeed in professionalising teacher education. Despite several challenges, ample opportunities exist to enhance teacher training quality. As the implementation of ITEP is in its infancy, the reactions of all kinds, from academics and beneficiaries, should be given an adequate hearing. If necessary, modifications in the implementation should be left to the state and institutions.

Collaborative efforts among the government, private sector, and civil society are essential to tackle these obstacles and establish a robust framework for delivering high-quality teacher education. Only through such concerted efforts can we ensure quality education for every child in India by equipping our schools with high-quality teaching professionals possessing the necessary skills for addressing the challenges of the progressive face of society and the global world. A quality programme on teacher preparation should be quick to respond to the demands of the society and community of the teachers, teacher educators, and potential teachers.

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